

TOOLS FOR ORGANIZING THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPING REFLECTIVE SKILLS IN FUTURE ENGLISH TEACHERS

G.B. Najmutdinova

Independent researcher of TDPU

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Abstract. *The article covers the theoretical and practical aspects of effectively organizing the process of forming and developing reflective skills in future English teachers. Reflection is considered one of the main mechanisms of independent thinking, self-awareness and professional decision-making in pedagogical activity. In this process, collaborative teacher-student activities, educational relationships, pedagogical games, reflective practice and improvisations play an important role. According to the results of the study, it was found that the development of reflective skills can be achieved through individual reflective diaries, brainstorming methods, business games and pedagogical support tools.*

Keywords: *reflection, individual reflective, reflective skills.*

Introduction: The successful professional formation of the personality of an English teacher, an adequate assessment of himself and his professional activity, that is, the extent to which he reflects on all important aspects of it - depends on the means of organizing the processes of developing reflective skills.

The mechanisms for organizing the processes of developing reflective skills in future English teachers are considered as a system consisting of the most effective technologies based on scientific and technical achievements, all scientifically proven tools that teachers prefer in their work. In this case, on the one hand, collaborative activities in the process of developing reflective skills, and on the other hand, educational relations play an important role in improving the processes of developing reflective skills.[1]

The organization of collaborative activities of future English teachers with students in the processes of developing reflective skills, that is, the formation of subject-subject relations, is carried out on the basis of educational relations, and reflective skills develop in this process. The development of educational relationship processes is inextricably linked to the effectiveness of collaborative work between teachers and students and innovative changes in a reflective educational environment.[3]

Method: The effective development of reflective skills can be achieved through the subjective worldview and perception of the world of the future English teacher. Reflective skills occupy a deterministic (philosophical doctrine of objective reality, the relationship and interdependence of phenomena) position in relation to other professional qualities, therefore, the educational process in pedagogical higher educational institutions should be organized in such a way that from the first stage (course) future English teachers develop reflective skills in a special and systematic way. Here it is important to distinguish two forms of reflection: reflection in the form of a learner (in the place of a “student”) and reflection in the form of an organizer of education (in the place of a “teacher”).[2]

Currently, there are the following stages of organizing the process of developing reflective skills in higher education:

1. Suspension of activity in subjects (before reflection).
2. Restoration of the sequence of actions performed.
3. Studying the sequence of actions (actions) in terms of their effectiveness and efficiency, compliance with the set tasks. The parameters (size) of the analysis of reflective materials are recommended by the teacher or determined by the students based on their goals.
4. Determining the results of reflection. Such results can be divided into several types:
the product of the activity - ideas, proposals, identified patterns, answers to the questions posed;
methods learned or created (discovered) during the activity;
planning for future activities.
5. Verifying assumptions in practice for subsequent subjects.

An important factor affecting the effectiveness of the process of developing reflective skills is the abundance of forms that correspond to the age and other qualities of the participants in the educational process.[2]

If the student cannot independently carry out the reflexive process, then in this situation he needs an organizer - a teacher, whose goal is to help the student carry out reflexive activity, find his own opportunities and shortcomings. On this basis, educational (professional) tasks are determined. There are the following forms of educational reflection - group forms (collective training sessions) and individual (oral discussion of a situation, filling out a written questionnaire).

The development of reflective skills in future English teachers required the use of methods and tools rich in reflective aspects, in addition to keeping an individual reflective diary, introducing reflective practice, using the "Mind Attack" method, organizing special reflective seminars, and carrying out various control activities aimed at solving reflective tasks. [3]

Result: As an initial stage of developing reflective skills, we have implemented the most appropriate form for students to keep an individual reflective diary. We have proposed the following scheme of individual reflection:

1. Drawing up a work plan for the day, week (month).
2. Conducting an analysis of the implementation of the plan every day, every week.
3. Identifying the reasons for non-fulfillment of the tasks set.
4. Searching for ways out of the situation that has arisen.
5. Diagnosing and evaluating the results of completing the tasks set.
6. Planning work to be done for the next week.[4]

Analysis of the individual pedagogical reflection diary helps to identify the reflective abilities of each student. This program was implemented by future English teachers at the end of their third year of education.

In addition. To achieve the set goals, we also actively used the pedagogical support method, the essence of which is to help the student overcome a particular obstacle, focusing on real and potential opportunities.[2]

The basis of pedagogical support was a special manual designed for students' self-awareness. This was facilitated by self-diagnostic tests, special games developed from a reflective seminar, tests aimed at studying personal professional characteristics, as well as solving pedagogical reflection problems.

The application method also justified itself, the essence of which is the participation of students in conducting part of the lecture material together with teachers.[1]

In our opinion, one of the most effective forms of practical work on the development of reflective skills is pedagogical improvisation. Because any activity is organized on the basis of stereotypes or improvisation. Pedagogical improvisation is the process of transforming knowledge, skills, and competencies into specific pedagogical actions. In the educational process, many unplanned situations may arise that require immediate solutions. An English teacher who is not prepared for unexpected situations will be distracted by trying to avoid such situations.

During the pedagogical experiment, we widely used pedagogical games. In our opinion, a pedagogical game has a clearly defined educational goal and a corresponding pedagogical result, as well as one of the means of creating interaction between the English teacher and students.

Business games can be widely used as a promising direction for the development of students' reflexive skills. Business games combine social and subject content, model conditional activity, and model a system of interactions. The reflexive practical training includes such business games as "Consultation", "Using educational technologies in English".[4]

During the reflexive experiment, in order to develop empathy, we used tasks that required different manifestations of this phenomenon to a certain extent. For example, writing an essay in which it was necessary to express some past life experience.

Resolving problematic situations by expressing empathy in the solution of pedagogical problems not only affects the development of necessary reflexive skills and competencies, but also the development of the professional and spiritual qualities of the English teacher.[3]

Discussion: Reflexive skills are often developed through game activities. Researchers understand the game as an analogue of practical labor activity. The use of games in the development of reflexive skills in educational theory was developed by A.A. Verbisky. The subject of the use of educational and educational games is based on the understanding of the quality of human activity in the game, which is considered to be action models, creating business games with labor models and role-playing games (sociodramas) with dialogue models (psychodramas) [2].

To diagnose the reflexive skills developed in students, the teacher can use methods such as observation, question-and-answer, and analysis of the products of activity. Observation of students' reflective activity involves studying educational materials, overcoming didactic difficulties that arise in them, identifying the most basic and important events that occurred with them in the process of reflection, aligning the goals and results of the activity, as well as developing criteria for evaluation and self-assessment.[1]

Conclusion: Students can regularly use their reflective skills, for example, in the form of oral reflections, surveys or observations. In this case, both external and internal observation should be used. External observation is necessary to control behavior, it should be carried out by the teacher. Internal observation, or self-observation, is carried out by the students themselves and recorded in their reports on their activities.

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